

Spectrophotometric Studies on Reactions of Molecular Iodine with Some Tertiaryphosphine Sulphides in Different Solvents

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Reactions of molecular iodine with some mono- and di-tertiaryphosphine sulphides have been studied spectrophotometrically in the visible region in different solvents. Blue shifts in $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions in iodine have been observed. Complex species of the type 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 3 (ligand : iodine) are formed. Their stability constants and free energy changes have been determined by Job's method. Possible structural aspects of the species have been discussed.

MONO- and di-tertiaryphosphine sulphides containing sulphur as donor atom are known to form a large number of complexes with metal ions¹⁻⁷. Their reactions with halogens have also been reported⁸⁻¹⁰. In the present investigations, we have studied the reactions of molecular iodine with triphenylphosphine sulphide (Ph_3PS), tri-*p*-tolylphosphine sulphide (T_3PS), 1,1-methylenebis(diphenylphosphine sulphide) (MDPS) and 1,3-trimethylenebis(diphenylphosphine sulphide) (PDPS) in CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 and benzene. The blue shifts in $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions as a function of ligand concentration, nature of solvent and nature of ligand have been discussed. The nature of complex species formed, stability constants (β) and free energy changes (ΔG°) have also been determined using Job's method of continuous variations¹¹.

Experimental

Materials and method :

The ligands were prepared from reactions of corresponding phosphines with elemental sulphur in dry benzene¹.

For recording blue shifts, 3 or 4 ligand concentrations were selected for each of the ligands, corresponding to a fixed iodine concentration (Table 1). The iodine and ligands were dissolved separately in the same solvent and mixed at room temperature (25°). Total volume was made upto 10 ml. The electronic spectra were recorded in the region 400-600 nm on a UV spectrophotometer of type VSU-2P. From the plots of absorbances vs wave length, λ_{max} of each solution was recorded (Table 1). For determining the nature of complex species, stability constants and free energy changes, equimolar amounts of ligands and iodine were

TABLE 1—POSITIONS OF MAXIMA FOR DIFFERENT LIGAND CONCENTRATIONS

Ligand	Solvent	Ligand concentrations $\times 10^{-3} M$	(Ligand) $(\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*)$ nm λ_{max}	Blue shift $(\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*)$ nm		
Ph_3PS	CCl_4	1.02	512	8		
		2.04	460,500	60, 20		
		3.06, 4.08	455,450	65, 70		
	CHCl_3	1.02, 2.04	510, 505	2, 7		
		3.06	445, 500	67, 12		
		4.08	440, 490	72, 22		
	CH_2Cl_2	1.02	500	5		
		2.04	440, 490	65, 15		
		3.06, 4.08	440, 430	65, 75		
	C_6H_6	1.02, 2.04	500, 495	0, 5		
		3.06, 4.08	490, 480	10, 20		
T_3PS	CCl_4	1.19, 1.78, 2.38	450, 450, 445	70, 70, 75		
		CHCl_3	0.89	508	4	
			1.78	435, 510	77, 2	
	2.67, 3.56		435, 430	77, 82		
	CH_2Cl_2	0.89	430, 500	75, 2		
		1.78, 2.67, 3.56	425, 425, 425	80, 80, 80		
		0.89, 1.78	500, 485	0, 15		
	C_6H_6	2.67, 3.56	450, 450	50, 50		
	MDPS	CCl_4	0.89, 1.78, 2.67	510, 470, 450	10, 50, 70	
			CHCl_3	0.89, 1.78,	505, 500	7, 12
2.67				445, 500	67, 12	
0.89		500		5		
CH_2Cl_2		1.78, 17.8	430, 495	75, 10		
		2.67	430, 480	75, 25		
C_6H_6		0.89, 1.78, 2.67	496, 490, 490	4, 10, 10		
		PDPS	CHCl_3	0.84	505	7
			CH_2Cl_2	1.68	440, 500	72, 12
2.52				430	82	
0.84		500		5		
C_6H_6	1.68	435, 485	70, 20			
	2.52	430	75			
	0.84, 1.68, 2.52	495, 460, 440	5, 40, 60			

PDPS is insoluble in CCl_4 ;
Iodine concentration is $1.97 \times 10^{-3} M$;
 λ_{max} for free iodine occur at 520, 512, 505 and 500 nm,
respectively in CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , and C_6H_6 .

dissolved separately and the volume in each case was made to 50 ml. The molarity of Ph_3PS and

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TABLE 2—MOLE FRACTIONS, OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS (β), FREE ENERGY (ΔG°) AND RELATED DATA

Ligand	Solvent	λ_{\max}	Mole fraction		Mole ratio	Composition	E	E_{ex}	β	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (Calcd.)
			Ligand	Iodine	Ligand : Iodine					
Ph ₃ PS	CCl ₄	440	0.4	0.6	2 : 3	2Ph ₃ PS.3I ₂	0.780	0.990	2.69×10^5	4676
	CHCl ₃	440	0.3	0.7	1 : 2	Ph ₃ PS.2I ₂	0.260	0.289	5.16×10^5	3698
	CH ₂ Cl ₂	440	0.5	0.5	1 : 1	Ph ₃ PS.I ₂	0.320	0.360	7.5×10^5	7951
T ₃ PS	CCl ₄	440	0.5	0.5	1 : 1	T ₃ PS.I ₂	0.468	0.575	2.3×10^6	7311
	CHCl ₃	440	0.35	0.65	1 : 2	T ₃ PS.2I ₂	0.382	0.430	16.8×10^5	4396
	CH ₂ Cl ₂	430	0.5	0.5	1 : 1	T ₃ PS.I ₂	0.450	0.502	8.44×10^5	8079
MDPS	CCl ₄	440	0.4	0.6	2 : 3	2MDPS.3I ₂	0.090	0.117	3.04×10^6	6113
	CHCl ₃	440	0.32	0.68	1 : 2	MDPS.2I ₂	0.115	0.136	7.32×10^5	3906
	CH ₂ Cl ₂	430	0.5	0.5	1 : 1	MDPS.I ₂	0.175	0.187	3.73×10^6	8962
PDPS	CHCl ₃	440	0.3	0.7	1 : 2	PDPS.2I ₂	0.152	0.164	1.11×10^6	5516
	CH ₂ Cl ₂	430	0.52	0.48	1 : 1	PDPS.I ₂	0.214	0.234	3.75×10^7	10337

λ_{\max} ($\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$) for free I₂ in CCl₄, CHCl₃ and CH₂Cl₂ occur at 520, 512 and 505 nm, respectively.

T₃PS was $0.098 \times 10^{-3} M$ in CCl₄, CHCl₃ and CH₂Cl₂; that of MDPS in CCl₄ was $0.047 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of MDPS and PDPS in CHCl₃ and CH₂Cl₂ was $0.049 \times 10^{-3} M$. The two solutions were so mixed as to keep the total concentration constant and the absorption of each solution was recorded at the wave length where the complex absorbs in that solvent (selected from Table 1). From the plot of absorbance vs mole ratio with respect to the ligand, the ratio of ligand interaction with iodine was found and calculations made for β and ΔG° using Job's method of continuous variations (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

Nature of interaction: The nature of interaction between a ligand and iodine may be explained as follows. Iodine has molecular configuration [core] $\sigma^2 \pi^4 \pi^{*4} \sigma^0$ and it absorbs at 520 nm ($\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$) in CCl₄. On adding a donor molecule, two pronounced changes occur in the spectrum. A blue shift is detected in the iodine peak and a new peak arises in uv region which is due to charge transfer transition. The charge transfer band involves the transfer of a base electron to the iodine σ^* orbital. The blue shifts have been detected in all the solvents used and λ_{\max} given in Table 2 represent the maximum blue shifts i.e. the region in which maximum interaction takes place between iodine and the ligand. However, the charge transfer band location is not possible for the ligands used because of absorption by phenyl π -electrons and (PS) groups in the same region.

Blue shifts: The positions of the maxima of $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions for the free iodine and on reaction with ligand along with the respective blue shifts are given in Table 1.

(a) **Ph₃PS and T₃PS:** In the reaction of Ph₃PS with iodine in CCl₄, blue shifts of 10-70 nm were recorded corresponding to different ligand concentrations. With increase in the concentration of the ligand, the positions of the maxima shift to the region 450-460 nm. Corresponding to ligand concentration $2.04 \times 10^{-3} M$, two maxima at 460 and 500 nm were observed, the maxima at 460 nm

being due to complex formation while that at 500 nm (weak) is mainly due to free iodine absorption. No further effect on $\pi^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition was observed on increasing the ligand concentration beyond $4.08 \times 10^{-3} M$.

In the polar solvent CHCl₃, the free iodine absorption at 512 nm shifts to 510, 505, 500, 445 (doublet) and 490, 440 nm, respectively for the same concentrations as in CCl₄. The blue shifts for ligand concentrations $(1.02, 2.04) \times 10^{-3} M$ are of the order of 8-60 nm in CCl₄, unlike in chloroform, where the shift is only 2-7 nm. However, for higher concentrations, the blue shifts lie between 67-72 nm, somewhat higher than those in CCl₄. This means that for low ligand concentration, it remains solvated to a large extent with the polar solvent chloroform, but the higher concentrations shift the equilibrium to the right side leading to larger blue shifts and hence more complex formation. In the non-polar solvent, the solvation of the ligand is low, as expected.

In the still more polar solvent, CH₂Cl₂, the shifts lie in the range 5-75 nm and are of a little higher magnitude as compared to those in CHCl₃ and CCl₄. On changing the solvent from CCl₄ to CHCl₃, the shift is only 7 nm for the concentration $2.04 \times 10^{-3} M$; while from CHCl₃ to CH₂Cl₂, the shift is higher than that observed in CCl₄. Similarly, for higher ligand concentrations, the values are higher. It follows from this that solvent polarity plays some role in determining interaction between a ligand and iodine.

In benzene, the shifts are in the range 0-20 nm, which are much less in comparison to those in other solvents mentioned above. This indicates very poor interaction between the ligand and iodine in benzene. It may probably be due to stronger interaction between π -electrons of benzene with the empty antibonding molecular orbitals on iodine and hence weak interaction between sulphur of the ligand and iodine.

It may be seen from above that the blue shifts vary in the order CH₂Cl₂ > CHCl₃ > CCl₄ > benzene. The larger interaction in more polar solvents may

be due to stabilization of the resulting complex with dipole interaction, that is solvation. Analogous observation has been made in the case of sulphur-iodine interactions using thiourea as the ligand¹⁸.

Considering the next ligand T₃PS, expected to be a better donor than Ph₃PS due to positive inductive effect of methyl groups, the blue shifts lie between 70-75 nm in CCl₄ for similar ligand concentrations. This indicates that there is a strong interaction between iodine and the tolyl ligand, T₃PS as compared to that with Ph₃PS. In chloroform, the shifts lie in the region 4-82 nm. The shifts of 75-85 nm were recorded in CH₂Cl₂ which are higher than those in CCl₄ and CHCl₃. In case of benzene, the shifts of 0-50 nm were recorded. The shifts in benzene are higher for T₃PS as compared to Ph₃PS indicating stronger interaction of T₃PS with iodine.

On comparing the interactions of both the ligands with iodine, the shifts are more pronounced in the case of T₃PS. This shows that T₃PS is a better donor towards iodine as compared to Ph₃PS for the same solvent, which is in agreement with the expected higher basicity of the tolyl ligand.

(b) MDPS and PDPS: In the case of MDPS in CCl₄, the blue shifts lie in the range 10-70 nm which are relatively higher as compared to those of Ph₃PS in CCl₄. That is MDPS is a relatively better donor than Ph₃PS, but weaker than T₃PS towards iodine. Obviously, the replacement of Ph group by -CH₃- group would increase its basicity. In chloroform, the shifts lie in the range 7-67 nm. For the concentration 1.78 × 10⁻³M, the shift in π* → σ* transition is 12 nm which is much less than that observed in CCl₄ (50 nm) for the same concentration. This behaviour is similar to that of Ph₃PS in CHCl₃, but different from that of T₃PS for similar concentrations.

In CH₂Cl₂, the shifts are of the order of 5-75 nm which are larger than those observed in CCl₄ and CHCl₃. However, the shifts in benzene are of the order of 4-10 nm.

On comparing the basicities of these three ligands towards iodine on the basis of magnitude of shifts, it is seen that the basicity increases in any given solvent in the order T₃PS > MDPS > Ph₃PS. This observation is an agreement with charge transfer theory which predicts that the magnitude of the blue shift should increase as the donor becomes more electron releasing in character¹⁵.

The ligand PDPS is insoluble in CCl₄ and no studies could be made in this solvent. In CHCl₃, the shifts in the range 7-82 nm were recorded. The magnitude of the blue shift is more as compared to those in case of Ph₃PS, MDPS or T₃PS, indicating the basicity order towards iodine in CHCl₃ as PDPS > T₃PS > MDPS > Ph₃PS. However, in CH₂Cl₂, the shifts lie in the range 5-75 nm and basicity order is T₃PS > PDPS ~ MDPS > Ph₃PS. Finally, in case of benzene, the shifts lie in 5-60 nm range.

This shows that PDPS in benzene is having maximum interaction with iodine as compared to other ligands. Thus in benzene the order of basicity is PDPS > T₃PS > MDPS > Ph₃PS, being the same as in CHCl₃.

In summary, it is concluded that

- (i) in any of solvents employed, the basicities of T₃PS, MDPS and Ph₃PS vary as T₃PS > MDPS > Ph₃PS,
- (ii) in CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂ and benzene, the basicity orders are
 - (a) PDPS > T₃PS > MDPS > Ph₃PS(CHCl₃, C₆H₆),
 - (b) T₃PS > PDPS ~ MDPS > Ph₃PS (CH₂Cl₂),
- (iii) sulphur-iodine interaction in general varies in the order CH₂Cl₂ > CHCl₃ > CCl₄ > benzene, and
- (iv) the effect on π* → σ* transition was maximum for iodine to ligand mole ratios of 1 : 1.5 or 1 : 2.

Nature of complex species, stability constants and free energy changes: The wave lengths of complex absorption, solvents used, mole fractions, mole ratio, type of species formed, values of E (absorbance at maxima), E_{ex} (extrapolated absorbance), overall stability constants (β) and free energy changes (ΔG°) are given in Table 2. The mole fractions reveal the following type of equilibria.

In the solid state, Ph₃PS ligand has been shown to have 2 : 3 stoichiometry and 1 : 1 stoichiometry in CCl₄ and CHCl₃. However, our studies of Ph₃PS and MDPS in CCl₄ show formation of 2 : 3 complexes, and this lends support to 2 : 3 stoichiometry of Ph₃PS complex with iodine in solid and CCl₄. The 1 : 1 complex formation by T₃PS in CCl₄ may be due to its difference in Lewis acidity as compared to Ph₃PS and MDPS.

The monodentate 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 3 complexes can be represented as (I-III) involving overlap of a sp³-hybrid orbital on sulphur with an empty σ* orbital on iodine.

For 1 : 2 complexes with bidentate ligands, the structure may be represented analogously (IV).

The other complexes appear to involve complex structures.

The stability constants in different solvents vary in the order $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 > \text{CCl}_4 > \text{CHCl}_3$. The orders of stability constants for the ligands are (a) $\text{T}_2\text{PS} > \text{MDPS} > \text{Ph}_2\text{PS}(\text{CCl}_4)$, (b) $\text{PDPS} > \text{T}_2\text{PS} > \text{MDPS} > \text{Ph}_2\text{PS}(\text{CHCl}_3)$ and (c) $\text{PDPS} > \text{MDPS} > \text{T}_2\text{PS} > \text{Ph}_2\text{PS}(\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2)$. The ΔG° values lie between 3.5-10.5 K cal indicating weak ligand-iodine interactions. This data support the view that the strongest interaction takes place in CH_2Cl_2 , probably due to large solvation of resulting complex species. Similar observation has been made in literature for thiourea-iodine system¹⁹.

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